

SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE: CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

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ANNOTATION

In Uzbekistan, despite the instability of the world financial and economic system, high economic growth rates are being ensured, which confirms that the model of reforms chosen in the country has a correct and fully viable basis. In this article, the goal of the "Green Economy" concept is to ensure sustainable economic growth and increase the activity of investments, while simultaneously improving the quality of environmental protection and social integration. In order to achieve this goal, it will be necessary to direct public and private investments to environmental and social factors of sustainable development on a large scale. It was discussed. And also in the article, the features of digitalization of the green economy are shown as the main factor of economic development, but the role of innovations with the improvement of the quality of use of natural resources and nature is emphasized as the main factor of sustainable development.

Key words: Green economy, Greening, digital technologies, alternative energy sources, sustainable development, innovative development, global crisis, ecology, economic development, ecological culture, investments, national development.

INTRODUCTION

Further improvement of the country's economy and export of deeply processed, high value-added finished products is an important factor in ensuring long-term sustainable economic growth in Uzbekistan. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, in his report at the extended meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers on January 14, 2017, stated that "Further strengthening of macroeconomic stability and maintaining high rates of economic growth, including ensuring that the State budget is balanced at all levels, and that the national currency and the price level in the domestic market are stable providing is our most important priority." For the sustainable development of the economy, the lack of mutual balance between its various branches and sectors leads to inefficient use of economic resources in the country, which in turn leads to the occurrence of economic crises, the increase in the level of

unemployment and inflation, and the negative impact on the socio-economic standard of living of the population. 'causes to show secret.

Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of every leader's activity. Report at the extended meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers dedicated to the main results of socio-economic development of our country in 2016 and the most important priorities of the economic program for 2017 January 14, 2017, Tashkent "Uzbekistan". 2017, p. 8.

After all, the idea of "green" economy is not only for environmental economists, but it is a topic of widespread discussion in the world, and in this regard, great attention is paid to this issue in various political forums, by state leaders, political scientists. In today's economy, human needs are also changing, and turning to nature is of great importance in obtaining the necessary resources. "Green economy" is related to the need to prevent these changes from having a negative impact on the lives of future generations and to ensure better living conditions for them as well. If the economic activities carried out do not have a negative impact on the nature, it will have a negative impact not only on the life of the future generation, but also on the current conditions of the society. And otherwise, if humanity's attitude towards nature changes, ecological culture develops, production, service and consumption methods are adapted to "greening" efforts, this will turn our lives and future generations in a positive direction. changes.

"One of the main methods of "greening" the economy is innovation and the introduction of new technologies in various fields of activity. After the rapid transition of many companies to the digitization system of 2020, the stage of radical restructuring of the economy has begun. This means that the digital economy is digital is a new economic activity based on technologies, e-business, connected to e-commerce, producing digital goods and services.

Positive aspects of the use of digital technologies in the green economy:

- increase in labor productivity due to the reduction of production costs; - the creation of new green jobs, as well as the development of freelancing;
- creation of opportunities for increasing the competitiveness of companies, as well as expanding the possibilities of production of ecological products;
- elimination of poverty and social inequality. Therefore, the application of digital technologies to the green economy essentially leads to the creation of sustainable development technologies.

At the beginning of the 21st century, the United Nations put forward 17 global goals, which are interrelated priorities of human development. According

to a study by Oxford University's Global Recovery Observatory, supported by the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), less than 20% of total recovery costs are allocated to environmental issues. Decision No. PQ-436 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 2, 2023 "On measures to increase the effectiveness of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a "green" economy by 2030" was adopted.

The program of transition to "green" economy and provision of "green" growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was approved. This program is designed to achieve the following strategic goals:

- Reduction of greenhouse gas allocations by 35% from the level of 2010;
- Increase the production capacity of renewable energy sources to 15 GW and increase their share to more than 30% of the total volume of electricity production;
- Increase energy efficiency in industry by at least 20%;
- Reduction of energy consumption per unit of GDP by 30%, including expansion of the use of renewable energy sources;
- To significantly increase the efficiency of water use in all sectors of the economy, to introduce water-saving irrigation technology on an area of up to 1 million hectares;
- By planting 200 million saplings per year and increasing the total number of saplings from 1 billion, expanding green spaces in cities by more than 30%;
- Increasing the level of solid household waste processing from 65%, etc.

The Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the transition to a "green" economy for the period of 2019-2030, approved by the decision PQ-4477 dated October 4, 2019, includes a number of tasks to adapt to and mitigate the consequences of climate change, increase the efficiency of the use of natural resources, and protect natural ecosystems. . Also, the 15th goal of the National goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development in the period until 2030 is "Protect and restore terrestrial ecosystems, promote their rational use, rational use of forests, combat desertification, stop and reverse land degradation, and the process of biodiversity loss." "stop". This, in turn, is related to the effective use of tourist and recreational opportunities of the regions and the development of ecotourism.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In recent years, environmental degradation (climate change, desertification, loss of biodiversity), depletion of natural capital, increasing poverty, shortages of fresh water, food, energy, people and countries Problems such as inequality

between the two are the reasons why the current economic system is not perfect.

All global crises exacerbate pressing socio-economic challenges to stability in both developed and developing countries, such as job losses, social insecurity and poverty. The current state of the world, irreparable ecological catastrophes and huge damage to the environment require the need to transition to a "green economy". If we pay attention, we can see that the world's leading countries have already started the transition to a green economy. They have already realized that the green economy cannot replace sustainable development, but is a way to achieve sustainable development.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the experiences of many foreign countries regarding the "green economy" have been studied, and the implementation of many measures in the field of "Greening" is one of the most important practical issues within the framework of ecopolitics. In particular, the basin of the main rivers in our region and the reduction of biological diversity are causing serious concern. Evaporative gases and large-scale air pollution are exacerbating the problem. Today, no one doubts that the efforts of countries should be more active and effective in order to achieve the goals of "green development". Green economy is an economic system, the main goal of which is to develop all spheres of the economy while preserving the ecology of our planet.

Currently, global business is devoting large amounts of resources to the development of technologies aimed at preventing climate change and reducing environmental pollution. Alternative energy sources are renewable sources such as hydropower, wind energy, solar energy, geothermal energy, biomass and tidal energy. These resources, unlike fossil fuels such as oil, natural gas, coal, and uranium ore, do not run out, which is why they are referred to as renewable resources.

The total capacity of energy production facilities in Uzbekistan is growing, but the rate of development is lower than in major foreign countries. Uzbekistan is one of the most vulnerable countries to climate change, as 80 percent of the country's territory is covered by grasslands and deserts, so climate change can have a significant impact on Uzbekistan's economy. Since the early 1950s, the country's average temperature has risen at twice the rate of global warming.

It is necessary to develop the following measures to strengthen the role of the "green economy" in ensuring sustainable development in Uzbekistan:

First, priority should be given to projects aimed at providing the population with information about the causes of environmental degradation.

Secondly, it is necessary to help improve the quality of public administration in the field of environmental protection.

Thirdly, it would be appropriate to encourage the use of "green" technologies in the production and production of environmentally friendly products by conducting a "green" public procurement policy.

Fourth, "green" technologies should be effectively used to increase the energy potential of the national economy.

And finally, fifthly, in the process of modernization of the economy, it is necessary to increase the volume of state investments in order to increase spending on "green" infrastructure.

Sustainable development is a new model of organizing society's life, which can be achieved through the introduction of new innovative technologies into the green economy in the process of step-by-step transition. By implementing the measures listed above, we have no doubt that we will be able to ensure an even more advanced economy based on sustainable development for future generations.

According to UNEP research, the rational and efficient use of the world's natural resources will cost the next generation 2 trillion annually until 2050. dollar makes it possible to get economic benefits. During this period, the world population is predicted to increase by 28%, and the level of resource use per capita by 71%. As long as strict measures on rational use of natural resources are not developed, the annual consumption of metals, minerals, minerals and other resources is 85 billion. 186 billion per ton. can increase to tons. Investments in climate change mitigation could reduce this loss by 3.7% of GDP per capita, and resource efficiency could offset this loss.

For example, in Great Britain in 2005-2010 within the framework of special programs 7 million. tons of waste were processed and reused. This is 6 million. releasing tons of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, 10 mln. tons of primary materials and 10 mln. made it possible to save a liter of water. 8,700 jobs were created in this sector.

The process of transition to the "green economy" is of particular importance for each country and is directly dependent on such characteristics as natural capital, human capital and the level of economic development of the country. Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to create a favorable environment (legal infrastructure, incentives, etc.) for the transition process. If the stimulating factors used at the national level, including investments and public procurement,

are directed to the development of the "green economy", the process of greening the economic system will become more active.

CONCLUSION

Green economy is a new economic activity based on the further development of the economy related to production and service sectors while preserving the resources necessary for human life and health, the environment and ecology as a whole. direction is understood. In this case, it is necessary to carry out the following measures:

Firstly, in order to satisfy the needs of the population and increase their well-being, level and quality of life, it is necessary to increase the creation of material benefits without harming ecology and the environment.

Secondly, energy resources are needed for the development of production and economy, which should be increased at the expense of renewable energy sources, replacement of public transport with electric ones, construction of energy-saving buildings.

Thirdly, it is necessary to give special importance to the production of environmentally friendly products by creating environmentally friendly technologies that do not release harmful gases into the environment.

Fourthly, on the one hand, taking into account the limitlessness of human needs at a time when all resources in nature are limited, taking measures to expand the production of goods without reducing natural resources in order to ensure their compatibility is one of the urgent issues.

Fifth, in order to meet the ever-growing needs of the population, great importance is attached to the issue of how much to produce, how to produce, and for whom, while protecting the environment.

In my opinion, it is possible that in the near future, the sustainable development of a country will depend on the importance of using renewable energy sources in the energy network. "The process of transition to a green economy is of particular importance for each country and is directly related to such characteristics as natural capital, human capital and the level of economic development of the country.

Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to create a favorable environment (legal infrastructure, incentives, etc.) for the transition process. In short, in the conditions of limited resources and negative consequences of environmental problems, there is an objective need to form a "Green economy". The transition to the "green economy" allows for efficient use of resources, ensuring ecological balance, creating new jobs, and ensuring sustainable economic growth

References:

1. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 4, 2019 PQ-4477-son "On approval of the green economy strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period of 2019-2030".
2. Vaxabov A.V., Khajibakiyev Sh.X., Tashmatov Sh.A., Butaboyev M.T. Green economy. Darslik –T. "Universitet" 2020y. 31 bet.
3. TV Zakharova "Green" economy as a new course of development: global and regional aspects. Bulletin of Tomsk State University, №4(16), 2011.
4. Sustainable economic development in the conditions of globalization and knowledge economy: conceptual foundations of theory and practical management / Under the editorship. V.V. Popkova. Textbook. M.: ZAO "Izdatelstvo "Ekonomika", 2007. - 295 p.
5. Khaitboyev R. Ecological tourism. Study guide. - T.: "Barkamol fayz media", 2018. - 248 b
6. Brown L.R. Eco-Economy. Building an Economy for the Earth. Earth Policy Institute. W.W. Norton&Company. New York, London, 2019.
7. Decision PQ-4477-son of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 4, 2019 "On the approval of the "Yashil" Iqtisodiyotga o'tish strategy for the period 2019-2030"
8. Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Jahonbanki, Central Asia Mintaqaviy ecological center, 2022. plami. Jahonbanki:Washington D.C."

